

AI4

eosc

WP5 Final implementation report

Deliverable ID	D5.5 - WP5 Final implementation report
Work Package Reference	WP5
Issue	1.0
Due Date of Deliverable	31/08/2025
Submission Date	28/08/2025
Dissemination Level ¹	PU
Lead Partner	CSIC
Contributors	CSIC, UPV, PREDICTIA, IISAS, LIP, INFN, KIT
Grant Agreement No	101058593
Call ID	HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01
Digital Object Identifier (DOI)	10.5281/zenodo.16737951
Website	https://ai4eosc.eu/

**Funded by
the European Union**

¹ **PU** = Public, **PP** = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services),
RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services),
CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Prepared by	Reviewed by	Approved by
I. Heredia (CSIC)	A. Constantini (INFN) J. Saínz-Pardo (CSIC)	Project Management Board

Issue	Date	Description	Author(s)
0.1	16/06/2025	Table of Content	I. Heredia (CSIC)
0.2	12/08/2025	Initial version of the complete deliverable	I. Heredia (CSIC) M. Obregón (CSIC) A. Calatrava (UPV) G. Moltó (UPV) L. Berberi (KIT) B. Esteban Sanchis (KIT) J. Diez (Predictia) P. Castro (Predictia) S. Dlugolinsky (IISAS)
0.3	15/08/2025	WP5 internal review	I. Heredia (CSIC)
0.4	25/08/2025	First external review	A. Constantini (INFN) J. Saínz-Pardo (CSIC)
1.0	29/08/2025	Final review and acceptance	Project Management Board

TABLE OF CONTENTS

LIST OF FIGURES	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	6
1 - INTRODUCTION	6
Objectives	6
Architecture overview	6
2 - FINAL IMPLEMENTATION OF THE WP5 COMPONENTS	7
Authentication	7
Docker registry	8
Secrets management	9
Storage	10
Platform API	11
Platform Dashboard	17
AI4 Tools	35
AI4Compose	41
AI4 MLOps	47
Provenance	52
AI4OS LLM	55
Modules CI/CD	56
Metadata tool	57
3 - CONCLUSION	58
REFERENCES	59

LIST OF FIGURES

- Figure 1: Location of WP5 components within the overall platform architecture.
- Figure 2: Login page in the AI4EOSC AAI.
- Figure 3: User interface of the Harbor container registry.
- Figure 4: User interface of the Vault secrets management instance.
- Figure 5: User interface of the Nextcloud storage instance.
- Figure 6: Swagger UI of the production Platform API.
- Figure 7: Modules catalog of the AI4EOSC Dashboard (non-logged-in user).
- Figure 8: AI4Life catalog of the AI4EOSC Dashboard (non-logged-in user).
- Figure 9: AI4EOSC module detail view (non-logged-in user).
- Figure 10: Modules catalog of the AI4EOSC Dashboard (logged-in user who does not belong to authorized vo).
- Figure 11: AI4EOSC module detail view (logged-in user who does not belong to authorized vo).
- Figure 12: Tools catalog view in the AI4EOSC Dashboard (logged-in user of authorized vo).
- Figure 13: Example of use of the chatbot.
- Figure 14: Profile view.
- Figure 15: Overview section inside Statistics.
- Figure 16: GPU stats per model detail.
- Figure 17: Datacenters section inside Statistics.
- Figure 18: Graphs section inside Statistics.
- Figure 19: Nodes section inside Statistics.
- Figure 20: Modules catalog.
- Figure 21: AI4EOSC module detailed view.
- Figure 22: AI4Life module detail view.
- Figure 23: Federated learning with flower tool detail view.
- Figure 24: LLMs catalog.
- Figure 25: Try me list view.
- Figure 26: Try me deployment detail view.
- Figure 27: Standard deployments list view.
- Figure 28: Batch deployments list view.
- Figure 29: Inference deployments list view.
- Figure 30: Inference deployment detail view.
- Figure 31: Gradio endpoint for the AI4life model loader tool.
- Figure 32: IDE endpoint for the Development Environment tool.
- Figure 33: UI endpoint for the Computer Vision Annotation Tool.
- Figure 34: UI endpoint for the Deploy your LLM tool .
- Figure 35: FL training with Flower from AI4EOSC. Starting the training (log).
- Figure 36: FL training with Flower from AI4EOSC. End of the training (log).
- Figure 37: NVFLARE Dashboard endpoint.
- Figure 38: C4 architecture of AI4Compose .
- Figure 39: Screenshot of Elyra environment in Jupyter Notebooks.
- Figure 40: Screenshot of Node-RED environment in the Flowfuse instance of the project.
- Figure 41: AI4Compose logo.

- [Figure 42: Detail of coding a custom node in Elyra: environment variables in python code.](#)
- [Figure 43: Detail of coding a custom node in Elyra: environment variables in Elyra interface.](#)
- [Figure 44: Example of a subflow in Node-RED.](#)
- [Figure 45: Example of configurable environment variables for the Cowsay node.](#)
- [Figure 46: AI4EOSC MLOps implementation](#)
- [Figure 47: AI4EOSC Automated Data Quality Monitoring Architecture with DriftWatch](#)
- [Figure 48: Data drift visualisation of the OBSEA-FISH Detector Model from AI4EOSC Catalog](#)
- [Figure 49: Authentication and Authorization Flow for DriftWatch Integration](#)
- [Figure 50: Provenance Graph.](#)
- [Figure 51: MCP Diagram.](#)
- [Figure 52: AI4OS LLM chat interface.](#)
- [Figure 53: AI4OS CI/CD pipeline.](#)

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable describes the final state of WP5 components at the end of the AI4EOSC project, focusing on the technical implementation of each component, explaining their features, the software adopted, the architectural design choices and their interactions with other components.

1 - INTRODUCTION

OBJECTIVES

This deliverable (D5.5) describes the final implementation of the different WP5 components.

This deliverable is complementary to Deliverable 5.4 [D5.4], which is dedicated to the new features of the second release of the platform. While D5.4 focuses on the high level overview of the features implemented in the platform, D5.5 will delve into the technical implementation of the components. Thus, in contrast with D5.4, this deliverable will offer insight of the technical implementation of features also included in the first release of the platform.

ARCHITECTURE OVERVIEW

In this section we provide in **Figure 1** a quick reminder of the location of WP5 components within the overall platform architecture. Bear in mind that some components might be at the intersection between different Work Packages.

Figure 1: Location of WP5 components within the overall platform architecture.

2 - FINAL IMPLEMENTATION OF THE WP5 COMPONENTS

In this section, we will explain the final implementation of the different WP5 components, including a description on how the different components interact with each other. For a quick overview of each of the components, please refer to deliverable D3.4 [\[D3.4\]](#) where the endpoints for accessing the different components are provided, as well as the code repositories where the implementations described in the current deliverable are located.

Note that throughout the present report we will make reference to several WP4 components like the Workload Management System (Nomad) or the Inference Platform (OSCAR). For more information, please refer to deliverable D4.5 [\[D4.5\]](#).

AUTHENTICATION

The AAI of the WP5 components is based on Keycloak [\[keycloak\]](#). We federate multiple Identity Providers under a single Keycloak realm (ai4eosc). Currently the federated identities are:

- EGI Check-In [\[egi-checkin\]](#),
- EduGain credentials [\[edugain\]](#),
- Github [\[github\]](#), Google Accounts [\[google-accounts\]](#),
- IFCA SSO [\[ifca-ssol\]](#),
- SIESTA SSO [\[siesta-ssol\]](#),

Figure 2: Login page in the AI4EOSC AAI.

Each user registered in Keycloak has defined roles (“Realm roles”) that allow them to access given services within the platform, for example:

- “platform-access” to access the Dashboard,
- “inference-access” to access the Inference Platform,
- “nextcloud-access” to access the storage,
- “demo-access” to access all services in demo mode.

Based on the Identity Provider chosen by the user and the entitlements provided, we automatically assign roles in Keycloak. This allows us to easily onboard members of some communities due to our trust to that community as a whole. For additional flexibility, roles can also be assigned case by case.

For the time being, all Identity Providers get the basic “demo-access” role. Additionally, in case of EGI Check-In users, if they belong to either one of the supported Virtual Organizations (AI4EOSC, iMagine [\[imagine\]](#), AI4Life [\[ai4life\]](#)) they get full platform access automatically. AI4EOSC membership is managed at EGI Check-In VO level for backward compatibility, as this was the IAM system that was initially used in the project.

In the future, when more resources will be integrated, users coming from EduGAIN might automatically be granted intermediate level access, due to their trusted researcher status.

Currently Keycloak has 118 registered users.

In addition to user registration, Keycloak is also in charge of the definition of the application clients of the different components. For this one has to configure parameters like web origin, redirect url, etc. We follow the approach of having a single client per component, separating development clients from production clients for extra security.

DOCKER REGISTRY

The AI4EOSC Platform has deployed its own Docker container registry based on Harbor [\[harbor\]](#) and integrated with the AI4EOSC AAI ([Authentication](#)). This is done to avoid the limits of DockerHub (limits in number of collaborators, quota limits, etc).

Figure 3: User interface of the Harbor container registry.

The registry is organized in the following main projects:

- In the **ai4os** project, we store the images of the different platform components and related services (e.g. the AI4EOSC Dashboard docker image). Those images are automatically built from the relevant Github repos using Github Actions [\[github-actions\]](#). We also mirror those images in DockerHub to have a backup in case the registry suffers an unexpected downtime.
- In the **ai4os-hub** project, we store the images of the user-developed AI modules, built directly from the Jenkins CI/CD pipeline ([Modules CI/CD](#)). Again those images are mirrored to DockerHub as a backup.
- In the **user-snapshots** project, we save the images the users create when they decide to shelve a deployment in the Dashboard ([Platform Dashboard](#)). As those images might contain sensitive information, the visibility to the project is set to private. The image creation is triggered by the API ([Platform API](#)), which launches a Nomad job where the user deployment is located and creates a snapshot using the docker commit functionality. As those images are private, this project is not mirrored in DockerHub.

SECRETS MANAGEMENT

The AI4EOSC Platform has deployed its own Vault instance [\[vault\]](#) to manage all platform-related secrets and it is integrated with the AI4EOSC Keycloak ([Authentication](#)).

In Vault, each user has its own userspace, only accessible by them. Whenever a user gives permissions to a service (by logging to the service and emitting an OIDC token), the service can retrieve or update the user's secrets if needed.

Figure 4: User interface of the Vault secrets management instance.

The secrets management system is currently used by several services:

- The **Platform Dashboard** uses the service to store different kind of secrets:
 - It saves the RCLONE credentials [**rclone**] whenever a user decides to link a particular storage (**Storage**);
 - It saves the Huggingface token [**hugging-face**] to authenticate when doing LLM model downloads;
 - It saves the authentication token for the Flower federated learning tool (**Federated Learning with Flower**), for clients to authenticate with the server. The secrets can be generated and revoked directly from the dashboard for this purpose.
- The MLflow instance uses the service to store the login credentials, as the MLflow instance could not be integrated with the AI4EOSC AAI due to limitations in the MLflow software (**Experiment Tracking and Model Registry**).

All services interact with the Vault instance through predefined routes in the **Platform API**.

STORAGE

The AI4EOSC Platform has deployed its own Nextcloud instance [**nextcloud**] and it is integrated with the AI4EOSC Keycloak (**Authentication**).

The users are automatically assigned to a group called “ai4eosc” when they initially register into the Nextcloud. Currently, they are manually enabled (approved) by the WP6 leader although development is ongoing to automatically approve users based on their roles in Keycloak.

Figure 5: User interface of the Nextcloud storage instance.

The storage has a total 50TB capacity (extensible) and 500GB quota per user (also extensible case by case).

The storage interacts in several ways with the rest of the components. The Dashboard uses Nextcloud's Login Flow to generate an app password. These credentials are saved in Vault where they can be later injected in the Nomad jobs to mount Nextcloud as a remote filesystem using RCLONE. The mounted filesystem is used:

- By users to access their files, for example to read a dataset to train an AI model or to re-train a module;
- By Nomad sidecar tasks, to download datasets requests by users during the configuration form;
- By tools deployed as Nomad jobs, like for example CVAT accessing storage to automatically save backups of user annotations.

PLATFORM API

The AI4EOSC Platform API orchestrates the different elements of the platform, managing the necessary integrations to make them compatible. It is mainly designed to serve as a backend for the [Platform Dashboard](#), although it is used also by other components (e.g. used by the [Experiment Tracking and Model Registry](#) as an intermediary to interact with the [Secrets Management](#)).

The API is developed in Python [\[python\]](#) using FastAPI [\[fastapi\]](#). When available, the API uses dedicated Python clients to interact with the different platform components:

- *python-nomad* [\[py-nomad\]](#) to interact with the Workload Management System (Nomad),
- *oscar_python* [\[py-oscar\]](#) to interact with the Inference Platform (OSCAR),
- *hvac* [\[py-hvac\]](#) to interact with the Secrets Management (Vault),
- *harborapi* [\[py-harbor\]](#) for Harbor,
- *openai* [\[py-openai\]](#) for the AI4OS LLM.

API routes

PAPI supports calls to a wide variety of routes, accessible through HTTP calls and interactively via a Swagger UI [\[swagger\]](#).

AI4EOSC Platform API master@72fb3 OAS 3.1
/openapi.json

AI4 | EOSC

This is the Platform API for interacting with the AI4EOSC services. It aims at providing a stable UI, effectively decoupling the services offered by the project from the underlying tools we use to provide them (ie. Nomad).

You can also access the functionalities of the API through our dashboards:
- [AI4EOSC Dashboard](#)
- [iImagine Dashboard](#)

For more information, please visit:
- [AI4EOSC Homepage](#)
- [API Github repository](#)

Acknowledgements
This work is co-funded by [AI4EOSC](#) project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe 2022 research and innovation programme under agreement No 101058593

PAPI version: [ai4-papi/master@72fb3](#)

Authorize

Catalog (modules)

- GET** `/v1/catalog/modules` Get Filtered List
- GET** `/v1/catalog/modules/detail` Get Summary
- GET** `/v1/catalog/modules/{item_name}/metadata` Get Metadata
- GET** `/v1/catalog/modules/{item_name}/config` Get Config
- PUT** `/v1/catalog/modules/refresh` Refresh Catalog

Catalog (tools)

- GET** `/v1/catalog/tools` Get Filtered List
- GET** `/v1/catalog/tools/detail` Get Summary
- GET** `/v1/catalog/tools/{item_name}/metadata` Get Metadata
- GET** `/v1/catalog/tools/{item_name}/config` Get Config
- PUT** `/v1/catalog/tools/refresh` Refresh Catalog

Figure 6: Swagger UI of the production Platform API.

Routes are organized as following:

Catalog

The catalog endpoint is shared among modules and tools, as both items share the same indexing and metadata methods. The endpoint allows to:

- Retrieve the available items from the catalog. For this we parse the relevant git submodules repo, either for AI modules or tools [\[ai4-catalogs\]](#). The list is cached to deliver subsequent fast responses.
- Retrieve the metadata of each module. For this we retrieve the metadata file in the Github repo of each item, and validate it with the AI4OS [metadata tool](#) before returning it. Metadata is cached to deliver subsequent fast responses.
- Retrieve the configuration needed to deploy the given item in Nomad. This allows the Platform Dashboard to build the user configuration form, filling with default values and options. All modules have a common configuration structure, while the tool configuration is specific for each tool. All configurations are defined in YAML files.
- Update the cached values. When a new module is added to the catalog, the Jenkins CI/CD pipeline can call this endpoint to refresh the catalog index. Similarly, when an existing module is updated, the Jenkins CI/CD pipeline can call this endpoint to refresh the module's metadata.

Deployments (standard)

Standard deployments are Nomad deployments that persist through time. The deployment (standard) endpoint is shared among modules and tools, as both are meant to be used persistently. The endpoint allows to:

- Create a new deployment of a module in Nomad. For this we read the submitted configuration, check the requested resources are within quotas, replace the configuration in the Nomad job templates and perform final checks.
- Get all existing deployments in Nomad. For this, we retrieve the Nomad job information and enrich it with additional information (e.g. checks on whether the jobs endpoints are active or not).
- Delete an existing deployment in Nomad.

Nomad job templates are common for all AI modules and specific for each one of the tools (more information about those in the [AI4 Tools](#) section). In the case AI modules, the Nomad job includes:

- Constraints to force the final datacenter, depending on the project the user belongs to;
- Constraints on the node type, for example to avoid using GPU nodes in CPU nodes or to avoid some nodes that have special purposes;
- A section defining the endpoints to be exposed, based on the user configuration;
- A sidecar task that mounts and unmounts the user storage ([Storage](#)) inside the deployment using rclone [\[rclone\]](#);
- A sidecar task that downloads a user selected dataset into that storage, so that the dataset is ready to use when the user opens the deployment;

- A sidecar task that notifies the user if the deployment took more than 1 week to deploy;
- The main task that deploys the user's AI module. This task get a larger share of resources (RAM, GPUs) and is injected with user credentials (IDE, MLflow, rclone);
- A UI task that shows a Gradio interface, in the cases where the main task is deploying the DEEPaaS API as a backend.

Deployments (batch)

Batch deployments are deployments that execute a single task and then are automatically deleted. The deployment (batch) endpoint is exclusive to AI modules, since it is designed for training the AI module and freeing the resource. The endpoint allows to:

- Create a batch deployment in Nomad. For this we read the submitted configuration, check the requested resources are within quotas, replace the configuration in the Nomad job templates and perform final checks.
- List all batch deployments.
- Delete batch deployments, in case the user wants to delete it before it gets automatically deleted once the job is completed.

Batch Nomad jobs are very similar to the standard Nomad jobs, except that:

- Nomad job is type "batch" instead of type "service",
- Instead of launching a predefined service (DEEPaaS, IDE), we execute a bash script provided by the user,
- We deploy in special nodes with powerful GPUs, exclusively dedicated to batch workload

Try-me

The try-me endpoint is exclusive to AI modules. The endpoint allows to:

- Create a try-me deployment in Nomad. This is similar to a standard deployment but has a limited duration (typically 10 minutes). The deploy launches the DEEPaaS API of that module together with a Gradio interface for easy usage. Deployments are created in dedicated nodes that prefetch Docker images for faster deployment.
- List try-me deployments.
- Delete try-me deployments.

Snapshots

Snapshots allow users to create saved versions of the current state of their deployments, in the form of new Docker images. The snapshots endpoint is only available for modules, as tools are usually complex multi-image deployments that cannot be backed up using this simple strategy. The endpoint allows to:

- Create a new snapshot of an existing deployment. This we check that the user is within the Harbor registry quota and then launch a job in the same node as the target deployment to be saved. The Nomad job first checks the size of the

newly generated snapshot and then uploads the snapshot to the Harbor registry ([Docker registry](#));

- List existing snapshots, either the ones that are in the process of being created in Nomad or the ones already created in Harbor;
- Delete snapshots.

Inference

The inference endpoint allows to manage serverless services in the AI4OS Inference component. The endpoint allows to:

- Retrieve the configuration needed to create a new service;
- Create or update services. To create a new service, we read the submitted configuration, check the requested resources are within quotas, and replace the configuration in the FDL template;
- List existing services;
- Delete services.

The FDL definition is common for all AI modules:

- Defines the resources to dedicate to the service, as well as additional configurations;
- It checks that the module is indeed deployable (by checking if the software versions are up to date);
- It defines the inference pipeline, where one reads the input parameters from the call (in case of sync calls) or from the MinIO storage (in case of async calls) and executes the inference using the DEEPaaS CLI.

Storage

The storage endpoint allows users to interact via RCLONE with any storage provider linked from the Dashboard, particularly the platform's Nextcloud storage ([Storage](#)). The endpoint allows to:

- Remove any file from the storage. This is used by the CVAT configuration form to delete unused CVAT backups ([CVAT Image Annotation](#));
- List any file from the storage. This is used by the CVAT configuration form to list all existing CVAT backups.

Secrets

The secrets endpoint allows other platform components to easily interact with the Vault Secrets Management ([Secrets management](#)). The endpoint allows to:

- Create a secret;
- List all secrets;
- Delete a secret.

Several components make use of this service:

- The Platform Dashboard uses it to save linked services, like linked storage providers or Huggingface tokens ([Platform Dashboard](#));
- The Platform Dashboard used it to save token to authenticate clients with specific Federated Learning servers:

- MLflow uses it to save the user credentials.

Proxies

Those are typically endpoints where the API acts as a middle man between the Dashboard and the final service. This is done because we use a project bot that is authenticated with the final service, but don't want to expose the token to the user in the Dashboard, which is a client-side app. We currently proxy:

- Zenodo [[zenodo](#)], to be able to search through the dataset catalog;
- AI4OS LLM, to be able to expose a custom chat interface in the Dashboard;

Authentication

Except for catalog endpoints, which are public, all other endpoints are authenticated:

- Some of them are accessible to any user registered with the AAI ([Authentication](#)). Then checking the user roles, the API is decided if the user has enough permissions to use it. For example, users with "demo-access" role can use try-me endpoints but not standard Nomad deployments, which will only be accessible to users with "platform-access" role. Depending on the VO of the user, the job will deploy on a given namespace in the Workload Management System (Nomad) [[D4.5](#)], to make use of the resources dedicated to that VO;
- Others are only accessible with a dedicated token. Those endpoints are meant to be used internally by other platform components. This is the case of the metadata refresh endpoint (used by the Jenkins CI/CD pipeline) or the AI4OS LLM proxy, used to integrate the LLM with the Dashboard.

CI/CD

To automate the software development and delivery, we have implemented the following CI/CD pipeline components:

- Precommit hooks [[precommit](#)] to ensure code quality. We use hooks to enforce linting and formatting with Ruff [[ruff](#)], as well as the validation of YAML configuration files. We also use precommit-ci cloud service to ensure that the code quality is applied also to external contributions;
- Release Please [[release-please](#)] to automatically generate releases based on the commit names, following the Conventional Commits specification [[conventional-commits](#)];
- Sonar Qube [[sonar-qube](#)] for in-depth analysis of the code, including vulnerabilities, duplicated code, etc;
- Github Actions [[github-actions](#)] to automate the building of Docker images to the AI4OS container registry ([Docker registry](#)).

Reliability is a key factor for such a central component. For this, PAPI ships with an extensive set of integration tests, where all the described routes and possible user workflows are tested end-to-end.

PLATFORM DASHBOARD

The AI4EOSC Dashboard [\[ai4-dashboard\]](#) is a modern single web application that provides a visual interface to the users, so that they can access the platform resources in an easy and user-friendly way.

As mentioned in previous deliverables, it has been developed from scratch using robust web developer frameworks and tools, in particular:

- Angular [\[angular\]](#) to develop the single-page client application.
- Angular Material component library [\[angular-material\]](#) to achieve a uniform and clean look both in desktop and mobile devices.
- Jest [\[jest\]](#) to prepare unit testing.
- Cypress [\[cypress\]](#) to perform end-to-end tests.

The use of Angular enables a powerful and dynamic way to create the Dashboard by using components that are individually tested and can be reused, thus reducing code repetition and easing code maintenance.

The Dashboard can be easily customizable. This has allowed us to deploy custom versions of the Dashboard for specific communities like the iMagine and AI4Life projects [\[ai4-dashboard-ext\]](#). These communities will use their dedicated resources in the Workload Management System [\[D4.5\]](#).

The AI4EOSC Dashboard provides a public view for unauthenticated users and a private one for users logged via AI4EOSC AAI. Nevertheless, depending on the specific roles that the logged user has, they will be able to access some parts of the platform or others (as specified in the [Authentication](#) section).

- Non-logged-in users can:
 - Explore the catalog, which provides a complete relation of the available modules, tools and LLMs ([Figure 7](#)). Moreover, an integration with the BioImage Model Zoo [\[bio-image\]](#) (powered by AI4Life consortium [\[ai4life\]](#)) has been made, so that users can use those modules from the platform as well ([Figure 8](#)).
 - Check a module's detailed view, which shows additional information such as a description, its tags, links to the code repository, the Docker image and even the dataset if available ([Figure 9](#)).
 - Navigate through useful links located in the side navigation and the footer.

Figure 7: Modules catalog of the AI4EOESC Dashboard (non-logged-in user).

Figure 8: AI4Life catalog of the AI4EOESC Dashboard (non-logged-in user).

Figure 9: AI4EOOSC module detail view (non-logged-in user).

- Logged-in users (see Figures 10 and Figure 11) who do not belong to an authorized Virtual Organization (VO) can, additionally:
 - Try a module.
 - Deploy a module via the Infrastructure Manager (IM).
 - Deploy a module in the EOESC EU Node cloud resources.
 - View their current try-me deployments (status, access endpoints, resources), as well perform actions over them.
 - Check the platform notifications.
 - Check their profile.
 - Interact with the chatbot.

Figure 10: Modules catalog of the AI4EOOSC Dashboard (logged-in user who does not belong to authorized vo).

Figure 11: AI4EOOSC module detail view (logged-in user who does not belong to authorized vo).

- Logged-in users who belong to an authorized VO can, on top of that:
 - Create a deployment with their specific hardware requirements filling a configuration form (including modules, tools and LLMs). It can be deployed in batch mode or as a persistent deployment (standard deployment).
 - View their current deployments (status, access endpoints, resources), as well perform actions over them.
 - Access the statistics of their usage and the overall usage and resource capabilities of the platform.

In order to detail all the functionalities available, we are going to make a tour through the app, showing all the different sections and utilities that it has. The web is conformed by 5 main sections and 4 fixed components, which are static and appear in all of the interfaces (check [Figure 12](#) for details).

Figure 12: Tools catalog view in the AI4EOSC Dashboard (logged-in user of authorized vo).

These main components are:

Top bar

At the top of the page there is a notifications button where users can check important notices, and a login/logout button where users can also check their profile if they are logged in.

Footer

At the end of the page there are some useful links such as the version of the dashboard with direct link to the GitHub repository and the type of license of the dashboard, among other things.

Chatbot

At the bottom right there is a chatbot where users can ask questions about the project and the use of the platform. This helps them find information and solve issues or doubts they may have when using the platform, in a fast and easy way (see Figure 13 to see an example). This chatbot is connected through the Platform API to the AI4OS LLM which will be further explained in the following sections.

Figure 13: Example of use of the chatbot.

Side navigation

Menu where the user can switch between the different sections of the web and access to external sites related to the project. Using this navigation, users can access the main sections mentioned previously. Each section is detailed below from the perspective of a logged-in user of an authorized virtual organization.

Profile

Here users can check their personal information, the virtual organizations they belong to and which roles they have in each of them, and the storage providers they have linked their accounts to (see [Figure 14](#)). Apart from that, they can also link their Hugging Face [\[hugging-face\]](#) account and check their Vault credentials ([Secrets Management](#)), if they have previously stored them in Vault.

Figure 14: Profile view.

Statistics dashboard

The Statistics section, which can be accessed from the side menu, is divided into four tabs that group resource information into different categories.

First, the 'Overview' tab (Figure 15) provides general information about the cluster resources (Cluster Usage Overview). This information is displayed using pie charts that show the amount of resources currently in use compared to those available. Below this, detailed information about the resources currently being used by the logged-in user (Your Usage) is shown.

Figure 15: Overview section inside Statistics.

Additionally, the card displaying the number of GPUs includes an extra button that allows users to view usage data by GPU type (Figure 16). This information is particularly relevant since, in the field of artificial intelligence and neural network training, GPUs are the most important and in-demand resource for users. This is why such a breakdown is not shown for other types of resources.

Figure 16: GPU stats per model detail.

The ‘Datacenters’ tab shows an interactive map highlighting (with points) the places where the data centers that belong to the cluster and that provide resources to the platform are located (Figure 17). Clicking on any of such points opens a sidebar displaying relevant information about the data center. In addition to the previously mentioned resources, two new metrics can be seen:

- PUE (Power Usage Effectiveness): a metric that determines a data center’s energy efficiency. It is calculated by dividing the total energy consumption of the center by the energy used exclusively for IT equipment.
- Energy Quality: refers to how “clean” the energy used in the data center is. It represents how much carbon it emits—the lower the value, the better the energy quality.

Currently, this information is calculated periodically so it is not based on real time values. To help users to understand this type of information, especially when it involves technical concepts or requires further explanation, a question mark icon has been placed. When users hover over this icon, a tooltip appears explaining the concept.

Figure 17: Datacenters section inside Statistics.

Next is the 'Graphs' tab, which is divided into two sections (Figure 18). The first section, 'AI4EOESC Usage Over Time', includes seven graphs showing resource usage over time—specifically over the past three months. At the bottom, the user's aggregated resource usage on the platform is shown in comparison to the total aggregated usage.

Figure 18: Graphs section inside Statistics.

Finally, the Nodes tab (only visible to developers) displays the resources of all nodes that belong to the cluster (Figure 19). The nodes are divided into those that have only CPU and those that also include GPU.

Figure 19: Nodes section inside Statistics.

Catalog

The platform's catalog is divided into three different categories: modules, tools and LLMs. In each of them, there is a list of cards, one for each element, with basic information (name and description). These cards can be filtered using the search bar, which looks for elements with the searched text in their name or description. While these characteristics are shared by the three categories, there are also differences between them, as detailed above.

Modules

Apart from the search bar, users can create their own filters (based on metadata attributes) by selecting libraries, tasks, platform categories, data types and tags. They can be applied one at a time, or they can be concatenated so more than one filter is applied. There is a specific button (Additional filters) which opens a modal explaining how this works. Apart from that, modules can also be sorted alphabetically by name or by most recent (check [Figure 20](#)).

Figure 20: Modules catalog.

When the user clicks on them, a detailed page with information about the module is displayed (check Figure 21). Apart from showing all the metadata attributes related to the module, in this interface users can:

- Try the module.
- Deploy the module via the Nomad cluster, using OSCAR [oscar], the infrastructure manager or the EU Node [eu-node].
- Deploy the module using JupyterLab codespace.
- Deploy the module in batch mode.
- View the provenance graph of the module and download its RDF file.
- Access to additional resources.

Figure 21: AI4EOOSC module detailed view.

Apart from the main catalog, modules from BiImage Model Zoo are also available from the dashboard (as previously seen in [Figure 8](#)). In this case, users still have the search bar to filter the modules but there are no more complex filtering options, because these modules (as they are external) do not follow the same metadata schema [[jai4-metadata](#)]. Nevertheless, when the user clicks on a card, a detailed view with their specific metadata is displayed ([Figure 22](#)). These modules can only be deployed as standard deployments.

Figure 22: AI4Life module detail view.

Tools

As shown in [Figure 12](#), the tools catalog functions identically to the modules catalog. There are 6 tools available in total, which will be detailed in the [next section](#).

The tools metadata is displayed the same way as the modules, but no provenance graphs are provided ([Figure 23](#)). Apart from that, the only way to deploy the tools is as standard deployments.

Figure 23: Federated learning with flower tool detail view.

LLMs

The LLMs catalog is similar to the previous two, except it can only be filtered using the search bar. This is because LLMs do not have a detail view, since their metadata is smaller, it is displayed directly on the card: each model's link to Hugging Face, the number of tokens, and the license type (see [Figure 24](#)).

When a user clicks on one card, the configuration form for deploying the LLM inside the Nomad cluster (also named as standard deployment) appears. This form uses the "Deploy your LLM" tool which will be discussed further in the document (see [AI4 Tools](#)). Therefore, it is the same as the one described for that tool. In this case, however, the model selection field is pre-selected based on the card clicked by the user.

Figure 24: LLMs catalog.

Tasks

The platform's tasks are divided into four different categories, depending on their nature. Within each category, users can manage and perform actions on their deployments.

Try me

A Try Me deployment is a short-lived web UI deployment that users can interact with to test a module before launching a proper deployment. These deployments are also useful for logged-in users who are not part of an authorized virtual organization (VO), as it allows them to try out modules and view a showcase of the platform's capabilities before applying for a VO.

The list of try-mes allows users to check the information of a deployment, access the deployment's user interface, or delete it (Figure 25).

Figure 25: Try me list view.

In particular, users can view the deployment ID, its description, the Docker image it uses, and other details, such as the resources it consumes. (See Figure 26 for all the displayed information).

Figure 26: Try me deployment detail view.

Deployments

The default deployments are persistent deployments that users can interact with via an IDE. As it can be seen in Figure 27, these deployments are divided into three categories, depending on their type: modules and tools (which have different catalogs, as it was

mentioned before), and snapshots (backups of deployments that can be re-deployed). For each of them users can perform different actions:

- Modules: check the deployment information (same as in try-me), access the UI, create a snapshot and delete the deployment.
- Tools: check the deployment information (idem), access the UI and delete the deployment. Apart from this, deployments that use Flower have the option to manage the deployment secrets.
- Snapshots: check the deployment information (idem), redeploy the snapshot and delete the deployment.

Name	Status	Container name	GPUs	Creation time (UTC)	Actions
green_goat	Running	ai4oshub/semseg-vaahingen:latest	0	2025-07-18 08:14:23	[Refresh] [Refresh] [Refresh]

Name	Status	Container name	GPUs	Creation time (UTC)	Actions
lavender_rouse	Running	registry.services.ai4os.eu/ai4os/ai4os-mlflow-server:2.5-S9fo	0	2025-07-18 08:34:28	[Refresh] [Refresh] [Refresh]
bronze_cuckoo	Running	ai4oshub/ai4os-federated-server:latest	0	2025-07-18 09:34:20	[Refresh] [Refresh] [Refresh]

Name	Status	Container tag name	Size (GiB)	Creation time (UTC)	Actions
ivory_ermine	Running	0d472510-2ef6-11d0-9374-17227a59de7f_1747034936	0.53	2025-05-12 09:28:56	[Refresh] [Refresh] [Refresh]

Figure 27: Standard deployments list view.

Users can specify its characteristics using a configuration form. For modules and snapshots, users can define:

- A title and a description.
- Which service to run (Deepaas or Jupyter).
- Docker image and Docker tag (in the case of snapshots they will be the ones pre-saved).
- Resources dedicated (CPUs, GPUs, RAM and disk).
- Storage to connect to the deployment and external datasets to train the model with.

For tools, each of them has its own form with particular fields depending on the information they need (see [AI4 Tools](#)).

Batch training

Modules and snapshots deployments can be also trained in batch mode, which means that users will be able to create a temporary job that is killed after the training is completed. This allows for a more efficient resource usage. In this list ([Figure 28](#)), users can check the deployment's details and delete them if necessary.

Figure 28: Batch deployments list view.

Inference

The inference section shows the list of deployments which are deployed as serverless using the AI4OS Inference Platform—based on OSCAR (Figure 29). As in the previous deployments, users can also check their information, in order to access the synchronous and asynchronous endpoints (Figure 30), or delete them.

Figure 29: Inference deployments list view.

Figure 30: Inference deployment detail view.

Platform services

This part of the side navigation shows useful links which give access to useful AI4EOSC services. In particular:

- Storage: access to the Nextcloud instance.
- Experiment tracking: access to the MLflow instance.
- AI inference workflows: access to the FlowFuse instance.

The code relies on the use of Github actions to create a DevOps workflow that enables the quick additions of new features in a controlled and reproducible way. The two main tools used are the Release Please library [\[release-please\]](#), to generate releases based on the Conventional Commits convention [\[conventional-commits\]](#), and the build-and-push action, to automatically build images to DockerHub and the [AI4OS Docker Registry](#). It is also connected to a SonarQube instance [\[sonar-qube\]](#), so that a new analysis of the code is generated when a pull request is created.

The Dashboard interacts with the API to retrieve the displayed information. It therefore has correspondingly two deployed instances: one for production and one for development.

Finally, it is worth mentioning that a Plausible [\[plausible\]](#) instance was deployed [\[ai4-dashboard\]](#). It provides an easy to use dashboard where different usage metrics of the AI4EOSC Dashboard are shown. As it is no longer needed [\[plausible-gdpr\]](#), the cookie consent banner shown in earlier versions of the platform has been removed. Nevertheless, the access to the Plausible statistics dashboard is still private and the data of the users is pseudonymized, so it is still GDPR-compliant.

AI4 Tools

We have developed a set of tools to assist users in the different tasks relating to the ML lifecycle. All of them are deployable through the Platform Dashboard Tool Catalog ([Tools](#)).

Many of those tools have been developed inside WP4, so we will report here only as far as WP5 components are involved. We will describe the necessary configurations and how they are deployed from the Platform API ([Catalog](#)).

AI4Life Model Loader

This tool allows the deployment of external models in the AI4EOSC platform, in this case models from the Biolmage Model Zoo [[bio-image](#)]. To enable this, we have created a special connector that is able to read the model specification defined in the Biolmage metadata. With this information, we are able to create a template (based on the same templates AI modules follow), download the model and automatically define the interface with the DEEPaaS API.

The configuration form is divided in two parts:

- **General configuration:** here, the user defines the basic deployment parameters (title, description, Docker image and tag). Apart from that, the user can choose which Biolmage model to deploy.
- **Hardware configuration:** in this section the user can specify the computational resources needed for their deployment. These include the number of CPUs and GPUs, the model of the GPU, the amount of RAM and disk memory.

Once the Platform API receives that configuration and replaces the Nomad job template. The deployment will expose a Gradio UI developed specifically for this tool.

Figure 31: Gradio endpoint for the AI4life model loader tool.

AI4EOSC Development Environment

This tool allows for the creation of a custom development environment that the user can leverage to deploy their module. It allows you to deploy several IDEs and choose among many environment flavours (Tensorflow versions, Pytorch versions, etc). To improve user experience the VScode environment comes with many useful extensions preinstalled.

The configuration form is divided in three parts:

- **General configuration:** apart from the basic details mentioned before, users can specify which service to run (VSCode or JupyterLab) and what password to use in order to access the IDE.
- **Hardware configuration:** users can select the computational resources needed for their deployment including the number of CPUs and GPUs, the GPU model and the RAM and disk memory..
- **Data configuration:** in this section users can select which data storage provider they want to mount in their deployment, either from the linked providers or manually adding the provider via RCLONE credentials. Additionally, users can configure which datasets to download to their storage, by navigating through the Zenodo communities or entering the DOI directly.

Once the Platform API receives that configuration and replaces the Nomad job template. The template is very similar to the Nomad job template described for AI modules ([Catalog](#)). The deployment will expose the IDE endpoint, protected with a password.

Figure 32: IDE endpoint for the Development Environment tool.

CVAT Image Annotation

This tool enables users to label their computer vision datasets, leveraging the Computer Vision Annotation Tool [\[cvat\]](#).

Its configuration form has a single section:

- **General configuration:** apart from the basic details, users have to specify their CVAT credentials (username and password) in order to be able to create the deployment.
- **Data configuration:** in this section users can select which data storage provider they want to mount in their deployment. This is done because the Nomad job will automatically save periodic backups of the user annotations in the storage, in case the deployment unexpectedly crashes, so that the very time-consuming effort is not lost.

Once the Platform API receives that configuration and replaces the Nomad job template. Due to the high number of containers that comprise CVAT, the Nomad job template is unusually complex and is described in D4.5 [\[D4.5\]](#). The deployment will expose a single endpoint, protected with a password, where users can label their images.

Figure 33: UI endpoint for the Computer Vision Annotation Tool.

Deploy your LLM

Adapting to the changes in usage of AI since the beginning of the project, AI4EOSC has begun supporting Generative AI for users, either allowing users to self-deploy LLMs (this section) or by deploying a project-wide LLM for all users (the AI4OS LLM).

Both options use the same stack: vLLM [vllm] as a backend to serve the LLM and OpenWebUI [open-webui] as a frontend to expose the functionality to users. Due to the shared stack both options share many functionalities:

- Users can chat with the models, uploading files if needed;
- Users can use OpenAI compatible endpoints, both in vLLM and OpenWebUI, to integrate it in their own services.

In the case of the “Your LLM tool”, the distinctive features are:

- Users can deploy a wider variety of models ([LLMs catalog](#));
- Resources are exclusively dedicated to the user;
- As admin, users can configure the UI, create Knowledge Bases for grounded answers and Functions for richer experience.

Its configuration form has a single section:

- **General configuration:** apart from the basic details, there are some extra fields related to the LLM options. Users can choose whether to deploy both the VLLM and the Open WebUI or just one of them. Depending on the selected option, other related fields will appear (e.g. the VLLM model to use, UI access credentials, or the OpenAI API URL and key).

Once the Platform API receives that configuration and replaces the Nomad job template. The Nomad job is composed of the following section:

- A main task, deploying vLLM [vllm] as a backend instance to serve the LLM model;
- An open-webui task, deploying Open WebUI [openwebui] as the frontend;
- A sidecar prestart task to avoid launching the frontend before the backend before the frontend is ready;
- A sidecar task to automatically create the admin user based on the user-provided credentials.

Figure 34: UI endpoint for the Deploy your LLM tool .

Federated Learning with Flower

This tool allows users to deploy a Flower Federated Learning (FL) server to train their models.

Its configuration form is divided in three parts:

- **General configuration:** apart from the basic details, users can specify which service to run (Fedserver, VSCode or Jupyter) and the password they will use to access the IDE for the latter two. In this step users can select a docker image that provides client authentication with the server via tokens, so that they can be revoked or new ones created if necessary, in order to allow only authorized clients to participate in training. In this step, users can also select whether or not they want to monitor the carbon footprint derived from training.
- **Hardware configuration:** in this case users can only define the number of CPUs and the amount of RAM and disk resources.

- **Flower configuration:** this section contains all the aspects related to the federated training. Users can define the number of training rounds, the evaluation metrics they want to include in it, the minimum number of clients (required for training the model and required for the FL process), and the federated aggregation strategy to use. Apart from this, if the user wants to apply additional privacy enhancing techniques, they can select differential privacy or metric privacy, and set values for the noise multiplier, the number of sampled clients, and the clipping norm.

Once the Platform API receives that configuration and replaces the Nomad job template. The Nomad job consists of a single task that deploys the server, exposing both the server endpoint and an JupyterLab endpoint, protected with a password. [Figure 35](#) and [Figure 36](#) show the logs obtained from the server deployed in the platform when starting and running a FL training.

```
INFO : Starting Flower server, config: num_rounds=5, no round_timeout
INFO : Flower ECE: gRPC server running (5 rounds), SSL is disabled
INFO : [INIT]
INFO : Requesting initial parameters from one random client
INFO : Received initial parameters from one random client
INFO : Starting evaluation of initial global parameters
INFO : Evaluation returned no results ('None')
INFO :
INFO : [ROUND 1]
INFO : configure_fit: strategy sampled 2 clients (out of 2)
INFO : aggregate_fit: received 2 results and 0 failures
WARNING : No fit_metrics.aggregation_fn provided
WARNING : No fit_metrics.aggregation_fn provided
INFO : configure_evaluate: strategy sampled 2 clients (out of 2)
INFO : aggregate_evaluate: received 2 results and 0 failures
INFO : Only one metric has been entered.
INFO :
```

Figure 35: FL training with Flower from AI4EOSC. Starting the training (log).

```
INFO : [ROUND 5]
INFO : configure_fit: strategy sampled 2 clients (out of 2)
INFO : aggregate_fit: received 2 results and 0 failures
INFO : configure_evaluate: strategy sampled 2 clients (out of 2)
INFO : aggregate_evaluate: received 2 results and 0 failures
INFO : Only one metric has been entered.
INFO :
INFO : [SUMMARY]
INFO : Run finished 5 round(s) in 220.79s
INFO : History (loss, distributed):
INFO :   round 1: 5.583970471432335
INFO :   round 2: 6.996509150454872
INFO :   round 3: 0.2656736985633248
INFO :   round 4: 0.05117568452107279
INFO :   round 5: 0.11555016668219316
INFO : History (metrics, distributed, evaluate):
INFO : {'accuracy': [(1, 0.7894736779363531),
INFO : (2, 0.7894736779363531),
INFO : (3, 0.946315768517946),
INFO : (4, 0.9842105319625454),
INFO : (5, 0.9768421116628145)]}
INFO :
```

Figure 36: FL training with Flower from AI4EOSC. End of the training (log).

Apart from this, as already mentioned, this type of deployments have the option to monitor the CO2 emissions derived from their training, and to add secrets (that can be managed from the dashboard) to allow or refuse the connection of different clients. More information on the development of this tool will be provided in D4.5 [\[D4.5\]](#).

[Federated Learning with NVFlare](#)

This tool allows users to deploy a NVFLARE [\[nvflare\]](#) federated learning server to train their models.

Its configuration form is divided in two parts:

- **General configuration:** idem.
- **Hardware configuration:** in this section the user can specify the computational resources needed for their deployment. These include the number of CPUs and GPUs, including the model of the GPU, as well as the amount of RAM and disk memory.
- **NVFlare configuration:** in this section users have to define their login credentials for the NVFlare dashboard and Jupyter server instance. They must also indicate whether they want to make the project public or not, select the Docker image to use (optional), and specify the start and end dates of the NVFlare project.

Once the Platform API receives that configuration and replaces the Nomad job template. The Nomad job consists of a main task that deploys the server and another task that deploys the NVFLARE Dashboard, protected with a password. More information on the development of this tool will be provided in D4.5 [\[D4.5\]](#).

Figure 37: NVFLARE Dashboard endpoint.

AI4COMPOSE

AI4Compose is the component of the AI4EOSC platform that enables users to build composite AI workflows by combining multiple inference services into a single, orchestrated pipeline. Its main goal is to lower the technical barriers for creating and experimenting with complex AI workflows, while ensuring reproducibility, scalability, and accessibility—key principles of the AI4EOSC project.

[Dynamic view] AI4Compose dynamic view
 Tuesday, July 30, 2024 at 11:10 AM Central European Summer Time

Figure 38: C4 architecture of AI4Compose [c4-ai4compose].

To achieve this, AI4Compose provides two complementary visual programming environments: Elyra [elyra] and Node-RED [nodered] with FlowFuse, as depicted in the architecture diagram in Figure 38. Both tools allow users to define and execute workflows visually, without writing large amounts of code. Elyra is integrated into Jupyter Notebooks and is particularly suited to Python users and researchers working in notebook-based environments, as represented in Figure 39.

It is worth mentioning the collaboration made by the project with EGI Notebooks [egi-nb], a service that offers Jupyter Notebooks on demand. We have added to the base image of the service the Elyra plugin support, so all the EGI Notebooks users can access the tool and thus, use the custom nodes developed by the project. This work, together with the other inference solutions of the project, has been published in the EGI Inspired magazine [egi-magazine].

Figure 39: Screenshot of Elyra environment in Jupyter Notebooks.

In contrast, Node-RED, combined with FlowFuse, offers a language-agnostic, multi-tenant platform that fits better with IoT scenarios, external systems integration, or users who prefer a web-based drag-and-drop interface (Figure 40).

Figure 40: Screenshot of Node-RED environment in the Flowfuse instance of the project.

AI4Compose is fully integrated with the OSCAR inference framework (acting as the AI as a Service component), which handles the deployment and execution of the trained AI models. The nodes developed for AI4Compose abstract away the complexity of OSCAR by exposing only the essential parameters needed to interact with the AI models wrapped as OSCAR services. Synchronous services are called directly and return results immediately within the workflow. Asynchronous services use MinIO buckets for input and output, making them suitable for event-driven and

high-throughput scenarios. The user simply uploads the input files to the appropriate bucket and retrieves the results from the output bucket once processing is finished.

Figure 41: AI4Compose logo.

Since the earlier deliverables (D5.2 and D5.3), AI4Compose has evolved from an initial prototype into a stable and production-ready component, with its own logo and identity ([Figure 41](#)). The second release reported in D5.4 consolidates the final set of Elyra and Node-RED nodes, improves documentation, and provides ready-made templates and examples publicly available in the GitHub repository (see [D3.4](#)) to help users adopt the tools quickly. AI4Compose delivers a user-friendly yet powerful way to compose and execute AI pipelines, helping the platform achieve its mission of providing scalable, FAIR-compliant, and accessible AI services to the research community and beyond.

Developing custom nodes

The process to develop new custom nodes for the models of the AI4EOSC marketplace is different depending on the visual composition tool used.

In **Elyra**, it is possible to create new nodes in Python or in R. We have created all the custom nodes in Python, using Jupyter Notebooks. The process for coding a new node is very similar to writing any standard Python program, which makes the process straightforward for users already familiar with the language. Users can import any needed library (for example, `oscar-python` [\[oscar-python\]](#) to interact with OSCAR clusters). The most important part creating new nodes is the appropriate use of environment variables. These variables are essential because they allow end users the configuration of the nodes without hardcoding their value: for example, indicating the path of files to process, or determining the OSCAR cluster endpoint to be used. It is important to explicitly invoke the environment variables within the node's code ([Figure 42](#)) so that they are properly exposed as configurable input fields in the Elyra interface ([Figure 43](#)).

Once the new node is properly tested, it is made available in the GitHub repository, under the Elyra nodes folder, to facilitate their usage, as the content of a GitHub repository can be easily imported in the Jupyter Notebooks environment.

```

1 import os
2 import pickle
3 import subprocess
4 import sys
5
6 required_packages = ["oscar-python", "liboidcagent"]
7 for package in required_packages:
8     subprocess.check_call([sys.executable, "-m", "pip", "install", "--user", package])
9
10 # Update PYTHONPATH to include user site-packages
11 user_site = subprocess.check_output([sys.executable, "-m", "site", "--user-site"], text=True).strip()
12 sys.path.append(user_site)
13
14
15 try:
16     from oscar_python.client import Client
17 except ModuleNotFoundError:
18     raise RuntimeError("Failed to import oscar_python after installation. Ensure the package is installed correctly.")
19
20 endpoint = os.getenv("OSCAR_ENDPOINT", "https://inference.cloud.ai4eosc.eu")
21 cluster_id = os.getenv("OSCAR_CLUSTER_ID", "OSCAR")
22 token_file_path = os.getenv("TOKEN_FILE_PATH", "/var/run/secrets/egi.eu/access_token")
23
24
25 try:
26     with open(token_file_path, 'r') as token_file:
27         token = token_file.read().strip()
28 except FileNotFoundError:
29     raise FileNotFoundError(f"Token file not found at {token_file_path}.")
30
31 options_oidc_auth = {
32     'cluster_id': cluster_id,
33     'endpoint': endpoint,
34     'oidc_token': token,
35     'ssl': True
36 }
37
38 try:
39     client = Client(options=options_oidc_auth)
40     print("OSCAR client configured successfully.")

```

Figure 42: Detail of coding a custom node in Elyra: environment variables in python code.

Figure 43: Detail of coding a custom node in Elyra: environment variables in Elyra interface.

In **Node-RED**, the process to develop a new custom node is different from Elyra. First, it is important to note that Python is not supported. Instead, Node-RED supports JavaScript, and the structure of a node typically consists of two main parts: i) a JavaScript file containing the runtime code, and ii) an HTML file, which specifies the node's configuration UI in the Node-RED editor. However, in order to avoid the complexity of coding the functionality of the nodes in javascript, there is another option to create the custom nodes: by a *subflow*. A subflow in Node-RED (Figure 44) is a reusable group of nodes that can be encapsulated into a single component and then used multiple times across the user flows. This method allows to design complex logic visually, without the need to write low-level JavaScript.

Figure 44: Example of a subflow in Node-RED.

As with Elyra, environment variables play a key role in subflows. They allow passing dynamic values such as file paths, service endpoints, or credentials to the node at runtime. By explicitly declaring and using these variables inside the subflow, they are automatically exposed as configuration fields in the visual Node-RED editor, making them easy to adjust by end users when reusing the node.

Once the subflow is ready, we export the subflow in a JSON format. We can specify some metadata details such as the node's name, description, and appearance options. In order to convert it to a node, we have used a Node-RED node called *node-red-contrib-subflow2node* [subflow2node], that encapsulates in a .tgz file the JSON file together with other needed files (like the package.json file or the javascript launcher) to be executed as a standalone node.

The nodes are reusable components that can be published as *npm* packages in the Node-RED Library and imported easily into the Node-RED editor. This is why this conversion process is recommended. All the nodes developed during the project are available in the AI4Compose collection [ai4-nodered-collection] to facilitate their reuse among the community.

Integration with OSCAR

The integration of the visual tools with OSCAR is done through the custom nodes. Mainly, the nodes invoke an OSCAR service that has previously been deployed in an OSCAR cluster, since the nodes do not create the OSCAR services, just invoke them and retrieve the output results, no matter if the execution of the service is via a synchronous or an asynchronous call.

As we have seen previously, in Elyra we use the *oscar-python* library to interact with an already existing OSCAR cluster, like the OSCAR instance of the project [D3.4]. Thus, the first step before executing a pipeline is to create your own OSCAR client, configuring it with the necessary credentials and parameters to interact with an OSCAR cluster. A script is provided in the repository to ease this task (*setup_client.py*). More details of this step are described in the AI4EOSC official documentation [ai4-docs].

In Node-RED, the implementation of the interaction with OSCAR is made in the subflow. Then, the usage of environment variables facilitates the connection with OSCAR. As

shown in [Figure 45](#), we need to provide the details of the OSCAR endpoint, the service name we will invoke and the credentials (token).

Figure 45: Example of configurable environment variables for the Cowsay node.

Moreover, we have developed a custom *Template* in Flowfuse for the Node-RED instances which comes with all the needed dependencies installed and a preconfigured set of nodes containing all the custom nodes we have developed during the project.

It is worth mentioning that for asynchronous invocations of OSCAR services, instead of directly interacting with the OSCAR service, the custom nodes (both in Elyra and Node-RED) interact with the MinIO object storage service, causing the event-driven execution of the inference. In Elyra this is done through the Python minio library [\[py-minio\]](#), and in Node-RED, we use the collection of MinIO nodes [\[nodered-minio\]](#).

AI4 MLOPs

The MLOps pipeline to track, store, deploy and monitor AI applications in production (see runtime view diagram in [Figure 46](#)) is composed by three tools: the first one focuses on experiment tracking/model registry, the second one on drift detection and last one on drift monitoring.

Figure 46: AI4EOsc MLOps implementation [c4-mlops]

Experiment Tracking and Model Registry

The Experiment Tracking, Model Registry and Model Monitoring component is based on MLflow [mlflow]. It is a platform to streamline ML development, including tracking experiments, packaging code into reproducible runs, and sharing and deploying models.

Key features of the tool are:

- **MLflow Tracking:** allows users to track experiments as well as to record and compare parameters and results;
- **MLflow Projects:** allows users to package ML code in a reusable and reproducible form in order to share with other data scientists or transfer to production;
- **MLflow Models:** allows users to manage and deploy models from a variety of ML libraries to multiple model serving and inference platforms;
- **MLflow Model Registry:** provides a central model storage to collaboratively manage the full lifecycle of an MLflow Model, including model versioning, stage transitions and annotations.

We have deployed an MLflow tracking server primarily for experiment tracking. We added an additional layer on top of the MLflow server that enables users to self-register in MLflow via the project common AAI (**Authentication**) and to manage permissions to their experiments and models with other users. We implemented automatic backup of the in-use databases and enabled manual restore operations. The code related to the dockerized solution is available. The instance has the following

configured databases (along with current usage metrics):

- **PostgresDB:** storing objects like experiments (+20), runs (+300), metrics (+3000), parameters (+2700), artifacts and registered models (+30). Actual artifacts such as models or datasets inputs consume a space of 53GB.
- **SqliteDB:** storing users (+15), permissions for experiments and registered models.

We have integrated MLflow UI with the **Secrets management** component in order to secure the MLflow user credentials. Thus, users do not need to provide their credentials for each new deployment on the platform because they are automatically injected in their development environment such as Jupyter Notebook or VSCode. Securing the credentials in Vault has also enabled better retrieval of the information when generating the provenance files.

To further enhance the knowledge graph generated by the provenance solution (**Provenance**) with information tracked from MLflow like the metrics, parameters, model version lineage, we deployed an MLflow user agent that automatically assigns read permissions to all existing and newly created experiments and registered models. This is achieved through transaction-safe and efficient database triggers. As a result, the new agent avoids permission issues, which typically occur because the default setup for new users is "NO_PERMISSION." This default means that each new user can only view and manage their own experiments and registered models unless access is explicitly shared with them.

We couldn't interface the AI4EOSC dashboard with MLflow because it is not possible to store MLflow credentials (especially the password) in the browser due to privacy/security concerns.

With the feedback we have been gathering from users, we have successfully deployed the instance into production. We have published how-to tutorials in the project documentation [[ai4-docs](#)].

Frouros

Frouros is a drift detection tool for machine learning systems developed as part of this project.

Its main objective is to identify, during inference, any significant change in the previously learned concept by an AI model (concept drift), or changes related to the feature/covariate distributions (data drift) that can result in a notable decay in the model's performance. In this way, we can check if the AI model's predictions are not reliable anymore, due to some change between the relationship of the features and the target value (e.g. customer behavior change), if the data themselves changed or even if the dataset acquisition pipeline is failing (e.g. a faulty sensor). In any of these scenarios, it becomes imperative to retrain the model with updated data.

Implemented in Python [[python](#)], Frouros offers support for both concept drift and data drift detection. It has modules for:

- **Datasets**, where examples or real and synthetic datasets are provided,
- **Detectors**, containing a total of 32 detectors, including classic and some state-of-the-art detectors, thereby surpassing existing libraries in terms of the variety and number of implemented detectors. Detectors are organized into:

- concept drift detectors, which work in streaming mode. The detectors grouped in three families: change detection, statistical process control, window based.
- data drift detectors, which work both in streaming and batch mode. The detectors are grouped in two families: distance based and statistical test.
- **Metrics**, where custom detection metrics are implemented.
- **Utils**, where different utilities of the package are located.

The package is agnostic to the underlying ML framework (Tensorflow [\[tensorflow\]](#), Pytorch [\[pythorch\]](#), sklearn [\[sklearn\]](#), etc).

Driftwatch

DriftWatch as a drift monitoring service aims to provide users with a database where they can store and visualise the trend of statistical properties of their data (i.e. p-values for drift analysis). Secured with OpenID Connect (**Authentication**), the authentication provides compatibility with federated authentication and fine-grained access control for groups, scopes and claims. Users can download a python client package that permits easy and direct report upload within scripts and pipelines.

The second release introduces a comprehensive graphical user interface designed to streamline drift monitoring and analysis. This user-friendly interface provides advanced functionality through several key components:

The interface displays drift records in an organised table format for each experiment, enabling users to easily track and manage their monitoring activities across different projects.

Each *drift record* contains detailed information including:

- **Creation Date:** Timestamp showing when the drift detection was initiated.
- **Status:** Real-time monitoring state (completed, running, or failed).
- **Drift:** Clear indication of whether drift was detected (Yes/No).
- **Domain Tags:** Customizable labels for categorizing drift types based on specific use cases (e.g., data-drift, concept-drift).
- **Execution Mode:** Processing approach specification (streaming or batch).
- **Algorithm:** Detection method employed (e.g., DDM, ADWIN, KSWIN).
- **Actions:** Interactive buttons for detailed record examination and management.

The interface includes sophisticated filtering capabilities that allow users to:

- Filter records by tags to focus on specific drift types or experiments.
- Select from multiple visualisation options to graphically represent drift patterns.
- Customise plot parameters and graph types for optimal data interpretation.
- Generate comprehensive visual summaries of drift detection results across time periods.

The architecture in **Figure 47** illustrates an automated data quality reporting system where AI4EOSC modules (like OBSEA Fish Detection) processes images through a

DEEPaaS-based pipeline that includes an autoencoder for generating embeddings, a drift detector for monitoring data distribution changes (using [Frouros](#) for examples), and integration with the Drift-Watch frontend interface for visualization and experiment management. The system enables secure storage of statistical features through AI4EOSC Authentication, allowing users to monitor drift detection results across multiple experiments via a comprehensive dashboard that displays drift records, execution metadata, and graphical analysis tools.

Figure 47: AI4EOSC Automated Data Quality Monitoring Architecture with DriftWatch

The system integrates drift detection capabilities into AI4EOSC modules (exemplified by OBSEA Fish Detection) through a DEEPaaS-based pipeline that processes images via autoencoder embeddings, monitors data distribution changes with drift detectors, and provides secure statistical feature storage authenticated through AI4EOSC SSO, all visualized through the Drift-Watch interface for comprehensive experiment tracking and analysis.

Figure 48 demonstrates the practical application of our drift monitoring solution by displaying the results from the *OBSEA Fish Detector model [obsea-fish]* from the AI4EOSC catalog where a drift detector will signal that the underwater camera is dirty (the red data points in the right side) and needs cleaning. This model was developed by UC3o from the iMagine project. The step-by-step tutorial is available in the documentation page [\[ai4-docs\]](#).

Figure 48: Data drift visualisation of the OBSEA-FISH Detector Model from AI4EOSC Catalog

The monitoring service is flexible and supports most drift detection frameworks like [Frouros](#), EvidentlyAI [\[evidently\]](#), Alibi-detect [\[alibi-detect\]](#), River [\[river\]](#), etc. Users can also use custom dictionaries to describe and store their drift parameters and metadata.

The diagram in Figure 49 illustrates the secure authentication mechanism where MyToken [\[mytoken\]](#) serves as a proxy to enhance long-lived token security, facilitating seamless communication between OIDC clients and the DriftWatch service through a

Python client interface, with access tokens being provided on-demand and subject to audience-specific restrictions for enhanced security.

Figure 49: Authentication and Authorization Flow for DriftWatch Integration

Handling Authentication and HTTP protocols to interface the tracking server can be tedious. We have developed a public "**drift-monitor**" client to simplify this process for Python developers by providing a streamlined interface that abstracts away the complexity of token management and network communication. The library offers a convenient context manager approach that automatically handles authentication using MyToken credentials, establishes secure connections to the DriftWatch service, and manages the lifecycle of drift monitoring sessions. Developers can easily integrate drift detection into their existing workflows by simply importing the DriftMonitor class and wrapping their detection logic within the monitoring context, where both concept drift and data drift detection results are seamlessly transmitted to the tracking server with minimal effort code.

PROVENANCE

According to the National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST) [nist], provenance is defined as "the chronology of the origin, development, ownership, location, and changes to a system or system component and associated data."

The Provenance System for AI4EOSEC is a multi-component system designed to enable the AI4EOSEC platform to utilize the metadata of its modules for generating semantic graphs. This system leverages the W3C Provenance Ontology (PROV-O) and the RDF Mapping Language (RML) to translate raw module metadata into semantically enriched W3C RDF (Resource Description Framework) files.

W3C PROV-O

The PROV ontology [prov-o] provides a set of classes, properties, and restrictions that can be used to represent and interchange provenance information generated in different systems and under different contexts.

It has three main classes:

- *Entity*: is a real or imaginary thing with some fixed aspects.
- *Activity*: is an event that occurs over a period of time and acts upon or with entities.
- *Agent*: is responsible for an activity or another agent's activity.

These classes will relate to each other via properties like **wasDerivedFrom** (explaining the derivation of one entity from another) or **used** (to explain how an entity is being used during an activity).

W3C RML

The RDF Mapping language (RML) [[rml](#)] is a generic scalable mapping language defined to express rules that map data in heterogeneous structures and serializations to the RDF data model.

A Turtle (Terse RDF Triple Language) [[turtle](#)] file can be defined, containing the necessary rules to transform raw metadata, presented in a JSON format, into semantic RDF within a JSON-LD format.

In order to run this RML mappings over a metadata JSON, a RML engine is needed. For this we use CARML [[carmli](#)], a Java library in accordance with RML spec.

Provenance Software Components

The AI4EOSC Provenance system is organized into three distinct software components: the Provenance API, the Provenance Visualizer, and the Provenance MCP LLM.

Provenance API

Provenance API is the core component of the provenance service within the AI4OS-HUB platform. Provenance API allows the gathering of all provenance information related to a module or project and stores it in a postgresSQL database [[postgresql](#)] using a structured format based on JSON fragments.

We have developed this service using the Spring Boot framework [[spring-boot](#)], which has allowed us to follow an efficient development process and build software that is simple and easy to maintain.

This module has two main functions: fetching metadata and generating semantic RDF based on the PROV ontology. It can fetch metadata from AI4EOSC modules related to services such as Jenkins ([Modules CI/CD](#)), GitHub ([Catalog](#)), MLflow ([Experiment Tracking](#)), or Nomad [[D4.5](#)]. Thanks to the software architecture of the project, integrating data collection from additional services would be straightforward.

To trigger the metadata collection from a module, an external request must be sent to the service, with a payload containing the identifier of the AI4EOSC module from which the metadata collection should be initiated. We designed the fetching system this way to make the provenance system reusable for any other use case.

After the module metadata is collected whenever the provenance of that module is requested, the platform reconstructs the provenance RDF by applying the rules defined in a RML (RDF Mapping Language) file (executed by the RML engine, [carmli](#)) over the stored JSON fragments. This real-time mapping allows any changes made to the RML mapping rules to be immediately reflected in the semantic graphs (final RDF files) in real time.

Provenance Visualizer

Provenance Visualizer is a web-based tool that uses the semantic graph generated by the Provenance API to create an intuitive visual representation. This enables end users to explore the entire creation process of a module with just a few clicks.

It was developed using TypeScript [\[typescript\]](#) as the base language. We then used D3.js [\[d3js\]](#) to build the graph (Figure 50) and React [\[react\]](#) to create the exploration menus.

Figure 50: Provenance Graph.

Provenance MCP LLM

Provenance MCP LLM is a Model Context Protocol (MCP) [\[mcp\]](#) system that enables end users to ask questions about the final graph displayed in the Provenance Visualizer and receive coherent answers in natural language.

It is divided into two subcomponents: an MCP client, which connects the LLM with the MCP server, and an MCP server, which exposes functions that the LLM can utilize. In our case, two functions are provided: one that allows the LLM to retrieve the original source of any ontology used in the graph, and another that enables it to access the provenance RDF of the application.

If a user submits a prompt with a question about the graph through the Provenance Visualizer chat interface, the question is sent to the MCP client. The client then forwards the prompt to the LLM, which determines which function of the MCP server to

invoke—in this case, the function that retrieves the provenance RDF. Finally, using the context provided by the provenance RDF, the LLM constructs a coherent response for the user. Flow shown in [Figure 51](#).

Figure 51: MCP Diagram.

AI4OS LLM

Adapting to the changes in usage of AI since the beginning of the project, AI4EOSC has begun supporting the use of Generative AI-based tools for users, either allowing users to self-deploy LLMs ([Deploy your LLM](#) tool) or by deploying a project-wide LLM for all users (the AI4OS LLM).

Both options use the same stack: vLLM [[vllm](#)] as a backend to serve the LLM and OpenWebUI [[open-webui](#)] as a frontend to expose the functionality to users. Due to the shared stack both options share many functionalities:

- Users can chat with the models, uploading files if needed,
- Users can use OpenAI compatible endpoint, both in vLLM and OpenWebUI, to integrate it in their own services,

In the case of AI4OS LLM, the distinctive features are:

- Since it is deployed project-wide, it is integrated with the platform AAI ([Authentication](#)). To expose this tool to a wider audience, we allow any authenticated user (even non-project members) to access this tool.
- Since it has a bigger audience than the self-deploy tool, it is deployed on a bigger amount of GPU resources (four NVIDIA V100 GPUs), so that more models and larger models can be deployed concurrently. After extensive testing of the most performing open-source models that fit our resources, we are

currently deploying Qwen3-14B and Mistral-Small-3.1-24B-Instruct-2503 (which supports Vision tasks).

- As the AI4OS LLM is used in the Dashboard ([Platform Dashboard](#)) to answer user queries, we have created a version of Mistral Small that uses our updated documentation [\[ai4-docs\]](#) as a Knowledge Base to provide grounded answer to user queries on how to use the platform.
- We have integrated in the Authentication the creation of Fernet tokens to allow users to use the backend OpenAI compatible endpoints.

Figure 52: AI4OS LLM chat interface.

MODULES CI/CD

In order to have a consistent catalog of modules, we have a Jenkins CI/CD pipeline [\[ai4os-cicd\]](#) that runs every time a change is committed to the module GitHub repository. The pipeline is a combination of:

- **User-defined steps** usually ensure model quality, by performing tests using [tox](#):
 1. Code style analysis using flake8 [\[flake8\]](#);
 2. Unit testing with pytest [\[pytest\]](#);
 3. Security scanners using bandit [\[bandit\]](#).
- **Platform-wide steps** that are common to all modules:
 - Metadata validation using the AI4OS metadata tool [\[ai4os-metadata\]](#);
 - Rebuild of Docker images into the AI4OS Registry ([Docker registry](#)) and mirror to Docker Hub [\[dockerhub\]](#);

- Updating related AI4OS components, like updating the module metadata in the **Platform API** or updating the Docker images in the Inference Platform (see [\[D4.5\]](#));
- Archiving the code in Zenodo [\[zenodo\]](#) if a Github release was made in the code repository;
- Triggering the **Provenance** service, that parses the information from the rest of the components.

The complete pipeline is illustrated in [Figure 53](#).

The combination of user-defined steps and platform-wide steps gives us the flexibility to accommodate different user needs while also enforcing some common requirements for all modules.

Figure 53: AI4OS CI/CD pipeline.

METADATA TOOL

The metadata tool is a small tool written in Python [\[python\]](#) to handle the different processing needs when dealing with our metadata. It allows:

- To handle the conversion between different file formats (like JSON or YAML);
- To do semantic versioning of the metadata, by defining different metadata JSON schemas that continuously evolve to adapt to the platform needs;
- To validate any metadata file against a particular version;
- To map between different profiles and formats, like mapping to JSON-LD and Turtle using the MLDCAT-AP profile [\[mldcat-ap\]](#). This feature was developed in collaboration with the SEMIC support center [\[semic\]](#).

3 - CONCLUSION

In the present deliverable we have provided a comprehensive description of the final state of WP5 components at the end of the AI4EOSC project. For each component reported, we have detailed its features, functionalities, the software used and the architectural design choices that guided its development. In addition we have also highlighted the interactions and dependencies among the different components, showing how they complement each other.

The final implementation of the WP5 components has successfully addressed all the challenges and objectives raised in the AI4EOSC proposal, going also beyond them in several aspects. In the overall project picture, they form a coherent and unified software stack.

The achieved outcomes represent a significant advance for the AI4EOSC project and for broader scientific communities (especially within the scope of the EOSC), that will benefit from the tools and services developed and deployed.

REFERENCES

All references were accessed on July 31st 2025.

Note: Endpoints and code of AI4EOSC components are provided in Deliverable 3.4.

[D3.4] Deliverable D3.4 - AI4EOSC Catalogue of Services:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16737905> (reserved DOI)

[D4.5] Deliverable D4.5 - WP4 Final implementation report:
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16737936> (reserved DOI)

[D5.4] Deliverable D5.4 - Second release of experiment centric and WP5 composite-AI tools: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16737943> (reserved DOI)

[ai4-catalogs] AI4EOSC catalogs:

- Modules catalog: <https://github.com/ai4os-hub/modules-catalog>
- Tools catalog: <https://github.com/ai4os/tools-catalog>

[ai4-dashboard-ext] Version of the AIEOSC Dashboard deployed for external communities.

- iImagine: <https://dashboard.cloud.imagine-ai.eu/>
- AI4Life: <https://ai4life.cloud.ai4eosc.eu>

[ai4-docs] AI4OS documentation

- Code: <https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-docs>
- Endpoint: <https://docs.ai4eosc.eu/>

[ai4life] AI4Life Project: <https://ai4life.eurobioimaging.eu/>

[ai4-nodered-collection] AI4EOSC Node-Red collection:
<https://flows.nodered.org/collection/4pW6ET9DMHs0>

[alibi-detect] Alibi Detect: <https://github.com/SeldonIO/alibi-detect>

[angular] Angular: <https://angular.io/>

[angular-material] Angular Material UI Component Library: <https://material.angular.dev/>

[bandit] Bandit: <https://bandit.readthedocs.io/>

[bio-image] BioImage Model Zoo: <https://bioimage.io/#/models>

[c4-mlops] C4 diagram of the MLOps component:
https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#MLOps_dynamic

[c4-ai4compose] C4 diagram of the AI4Compose component:
https://structurizr.com/share/73873/2f769b91-f208-41b0-b79f-5e196435bdb1/diagrams#AI4Compose_dynamic

[carml] carml: <https://github.com/carml/carml>

[coventional-commits] Conventional Commits: <https://www.conventionalcommits.org/en/v1.0.0/>

[cypress] Cypress: <https://www.cypress.io/>

[cvat] Computer Vision Annotation Tool: <https://www.cvat.ai/>

[d3js] D3 JS: <https://d3js.org/>

[dockerhub] DockerHub. <https://hub.docker.com/>

[edugain] EduGain: <https://edugain.org/>

[egi-checkin] EGI Check-In: <https://www.egi.eu/service/check-in/>

[egi-magazine] Article published in the EGI Inspired magazine: <https://www.egi.eu/magazine/issue-03/ai-inference-in-action-deployment-strategies-leant-from-ai4eosc-and-imagine/>

[egi-nb] EGI notebooks: <https://notebooks.egi.eu/>

[elyra] Elyra: <https://elyra.readthedocs.io/en/stable/>

[eu-node] EOSC EU Node: <https://open-science-cloud.ec.europa.eu/>

[evidently] Evidently: <https://www.evidentlyai.com/>

[fastapi] Ramírez, S. FastAPI. <https://github.com/tiangolo/fastapi>

[flake8] Flake8: <https://flake8.pycqa.org/>

[github] GitHub: <https://github.com/>

[github-actions] Github Actions: <https://github.com/features/actions>

[google-accounts] Google Accounts: <https://accounts.google.es>

[harbor] Harbor: <https://goharbor.io/>

[hugging-face] Hugging Face: <https://huggingface.co/>

[ifca-sso] IFCA SSO: <https://sso.ifca.es/>

[imagine] iImagine project: <https://www.imagine-ai.eu/>

[jest] Jest: <https://jestjs.io/>

[keycloak] Keycloak: <https://www.keycloak.org/>

[mcp] Model Context Protocol: <https://modelcontextprotocol.io/>

[mldcat-ap] MLDCAT-AP application profile, <https://semiceu.github.io/MLDCAT-AP/>

[mlflow] MLflow: <https://mlflow.org/>

[mytoken] G. Zachmann, M. Hardt, and D. M. Gudu, “mytoken: Secure long-lived tokens for you—everywhere,” presented at EGI Conf., Poznań, Poland, Jun. 2023.

[nextcloud] Nextcloud: <https://nextcloud.com/>

[nist] National Institute of Standards and Technologies. <https://www.nist.gov/>

[nodered] NodeRed: <https://nodered.org/>

[nvflare] NVIDIA NVFLARE: <https://developer.nvidia.com/flare>

[nodered-minio] Node-Red MinIO collection:
<https://flows.nodered.org/node/node-red-contrib-minio-all>

[obsea-fish] OBSEA fish detection usecase:
<https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/catalog/modules/obsea-fish-detection>

[open-webui] Open WebUI: <https://openwebui.com/>

[oscar] Open Source Serverless Computing for Data-Processing Applications (OSCAR):
<https://oscar.grycap.net/>

[oscar-python] Oscar Python client.<https://pypi.org/project/oscar-python/>

[plausible] Plausible: <https://plausible.io/>

[plausible-gdpr] Plausible:
<https://plausible.io/blog/legal-assessment-gdpr-eprivacy#conclusion-and-recommendations-for-action>

[postgresql] PostgreSQL: <https://www.postgresql.org/>

[precommit] Precommit: <https://pre-commit.com/>

[prov-o] PROV Ontology: <https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o/>

[python] Python Software Foundation. Python Language Reference, version 3.12.
Available at <http://www.python.org>

[pytorch] Paszke, Adam, et al. "Pytorch: An imperative style, high-performance deep learning library." Advances in neural information processing systems 32 (2019).

[py-harbor] Harbor Python client: <https://github.com/unioslo/harborapi>

[py-hvac] Vault Python client: <https://github.com/hvac/hvac>

[py-minio] MinIO Python client: <https://pypi.org/project/minio/>

[py-nomad] Nomad Python client: <https://github.com/jrxFive/python-nomad>

[py-openai] OpenAI API Python client: <https://github.com/openai/openai-python>

[py-oscar] OSCAR Python client: https://github.com/grycap/oscar_python

[pytest] Pytest: <https://docs.pytest.org/>

[rclone] RCLONE: <https://rclone.org/>

[react] React: <https://react.dev/>

[rml] RDF Mapping Language: <https://rml.io/>

[release-please] Release Please: <https://github.com/googleapis/release-please>

[river] River: <https://riverml.xyz/>

[ruff] Ruff: <https://github.com/astral-sh/ruff>

[semic] SEMIC Support Centre,
<https://interoperable-europe.ec.europa.eu/collection/semic-support-centre>

[siesta-ss0] SIESTA SSO: <https://aai.cloud.eosc-siesta.eu/>

[sklearn] Pedregosa, Fabian, et al. "Scikit-learn: Machine learning in Python." the Journal of machine Learning research 12 (2011): 2825-2830.

[sonar-qube] SonarQube: <https://www.sonarsource.com/products/sonarqube/>

[spring-boot] Spring Boot: <https://spring.io/projects/spring-boot>

[subflow2node] NodeRed subflow2node:
<https://flows.nodered.org/node/node-red-contrib-subflow2node>

[swagger] Swagger: <https://swagger.io/>

[tensorflow] Abadi, Martín, et al. "TensorFlow: a system for Large-Scale machine learning." 12th USENIX symposium on operating systems design and implementation (OSDI 16). 2016.

[tox] tox: <https://tox.wiki/>

[turtle] Terse RDF Triple Language: <https://www.w3.org/TeamSubmission/turtle/>

[typescript] Typescript: <https://www.typescriptlang.org/>

[vault] Vault: <https://www.hashicorp.com/en/products/vault>

[vllm] vLLM: <https://github.com/vllm-project/vllm>

[zenodo] Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org/>

